

2015

APR-MAY

***Aarhat Multidisciplinary
International Education
Research Journal (AMIERJ)***

***(Bi-Monthly)
Peer-Reviewed Journal
Impact factor: 0.948***

V O L - I V I s s u e s : I I I

***Chief-Editor:
Ubale Amol Baban***

**ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION AND TEACHING METHOD OF
ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION**

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Abstract :

In the post-independence era, urbanization in the wake of large-scale industrialization has brought about wide spread environmental degradation. Industries sprang up all over Gujarat in the sixties in an unplanned fashion which uprooted hundreds of small and marginal framers following land acquisition. "The plight of the land losers", according to the HPC, "has been aggravated partly by inadequate negligible compensation and partly by the failure of existing policies and programmes to rehabilitate them adequately, economically and socially." Apart from this, most of the villages affected by land acquisition are suffering from inadequate or near absence of basic minimum needs, the rapid felling of trees, disappearance of greenery, destruction of village forests, indiscriminate disposal of solid and semi-solid wastes by industries in and around affected villages are leading to serious health hazards for the people. "There has been nearly no rehabilitation worth the name of the land losers' families", laments the HPC (High Powered Commission)

General Nature of Environmental Pollution :

Under the term environmental are included the earth surface, beneath the surface of the earth, the entire surrounding atmosphere and the natural and man-made structures. Whatever man has devised for his comforts on earth are polluting the environment in some way or the other. When we burn some pieces of wood or coal, then smoke is spread throughout the nearing environment. Factories have a singular role in spreading pollution through their gases and chemical refuses. Our rivers and human abodes are badly affected by the same. Various types of vehicles use petrol, diesel and Kerosene oil which give out gases and smoke polluting the entire nearby environment in turn. Our rivers' water at various places is polluted by our scientific

operations through which filths are coming out. Human beings and animals use such river-water and they fall ill and die prematurely. The Bhopal tragic episode of 1984 is quite fresh in our mind. This tragic event rendered thousands of human beings and battles, disfigures or dead. For selfish ends if certain persons, trees of forests are cut down. The earth, hills and mountain are being made vegetation less. As a result, the balance of nature is being violated. The environment is polluted by all types of loud noise. All these types of happenings have to be brought to the notice of young people.

The Aim and Nature of Environmental Education

1. To educate all concerned about the nature and dimension of environment.
2. To develop the right attitude in the people regarding the safety and development of environment.
3. To explain the devices for checking the various types of pollution.
4. To develop the skills for solving the environmental pollution problems.
5. To provide opportunities to individuals, groups and institutions for keeping the environmental undisturbed as far as possible.

The Nature of Environmental Education :

Under this head are included environmental preservation, and expansion, and developing the right attitude in the people about natural environmental and letting understand the values of the same : Under environmental education workable devices are found out for solving the following problems :

1. What is environment ?
2. How can it be preserved and developed further ?
3. What is pollution and how can it be presented ?

Nature of Environmental Education Curriculum :

In view of above, we may now determine the nature of curriculum for environmental education. In it the following items may be included :

1. The relationship between man and his environment.
2. Natural resources and their preservation.
3. Resources of tress; water and wild-life.
4. Planning of local, regional and national housing in such a way as to prevent environmental mental pollution.
5. Environmental sanitation.
6. How to plan factories with a view to avoid their bad polluting effects on the environment.
7. The nature of government policy for checking pollution.
8. Means of reducing pollution to the minimum level.
9. The nature of planning of public recreational activities.

Method of Environmental Education :

Lecture, Discussion, Project, Excursion, Outdoor-study, Exhibition and Ply-method may be suggested as some of the principal methods of imparting environmental education. Onwards we are explaining, in brief, the nature of these methods.

1. Lecture Method :

Lectures may be organized on some of the aspects of nature. This may be done by a teacher of the school or by some outside experts. The various aspects of environmental pollution may be explained in such a lecture.

2. Discussion Method

Under this method two parties are organized for discussing various issues of environmental pollution. One party speaks about the steps to be taken in prevention of pollution and the other speaks about the pros and cons of the same.

3. Project method :

In this method students of a class are placed in various group. Each group is assigned some problem of pollution, relating to wild-life, tree, water, disposal of refuse and dead human bodies or local sanitation. Each group makes its own suggestions for removing the pollution. If possible, the students are also encouraged to play their small role in eradication of pollution in some way or the other.

4. Excursion Method :

In this method educational tours are organized under the leadership of a teacher. In these tours certain surveys are made of places and spots which are directly related with spreading pollution. Each student may be required to maintain his own diary of the excursion, the contents of which may be discussed, later in a class.

5. Exhibition Method :

Some exhibition may be organized for creating an awareness in the public about the various aspects of pollution and their bad impacts.

Ingredients of Environment :

1. Balanced use of Natural Resources :

There has been a prevalent misconceived notion that more use we make of available natural resources, more the progress of the world. Actually there becomes an imbalance in the nature if there is an unrestricted exploitation of available natural resources. Y. Nondumma is right when she points out that this mis-conceived notion of the exploitation of the natural resources under the pretext that they are meant only for exploitation by and for human being,

will take the entire humanity to a point of destruction. As it will lead to the entire change in the environment.

2. Control over the Waste Material :

In every industry there is left enough material which is nothing but waste. This waste is either thrown into the water or somewhere on the ground. In both the cases the atmosphere become polluted either through water or through air. To have a control over such a waste material is inevitable if we want to keep the environment or face pollution.

3. Check on Industrial Development :

Industrial development brings with it environmental degradation and may be a menace for the humanity if no check in the right direction is made on this. Industrial development adversely affects the community and surrounding atmosphere all around.

4. Proper Utilization of Natural Resources :

Nature has given us coal, gas, oil and many other minerals, etc. As there is no limit to the greedy nature of the human being, he has started extracting every thing mercilessly and putting the same at his disposal without caring for its proper utility and the limit to which the same should be exploited, according to need and limit. The result is explicitly clear. At certain places there is drought while at other place there are heavy rains and floods. It brings untold miseries but man has still not learnt a lesson to make a balanced use of natural resources.

5. Pollution :

A World-wide Problem : "The United Nations has repeatedly expressed deep anxiety over the ceaseless pollution all over the world and the innumerable problems it creates. In the initial discussions on environment there were differences on the issue. The U. N. Conference on Environment, held in Stockholm in 1972, became known for controversial approach. Two leading U. S. environmentalists openly contradicted each other over whether too many people or too few resources were responsible for the world's deepening ecological crisis.

Obviously, the plunder of what Nature has built over billions of years has to be stopped. We need a new life-style with environmental ethics as an integral part of it, not only for this

generation but also for the future generations to live and enjoy the freedom of this planet and beyond. It is important in this regard to reduce the rate of population growth to one per cent from the present 2.2 per cent, as China has done. Industries generation high pollution should be moved out of the perimeters of cities. Environmental education should be made compulsory at every level of learning.

Conclusion :

India is unique in the context of its environment. This is because we have three key elements of nature in abundance. The first is sunlight and we have lots of it. The second is water and again we have lots of it (Yes, India is one of the best endowed countries in terms of rainfall), if only we can learn to hold it properly. And then we have excellent soils. These three elements, when combined properly, become the fountainhead of life.

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